

Water Pollution

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Water pollution is the contamination of water, Likes rivers, Lakes, Etc. Usually, as a result of human activities, it negatively affects its legitimate uses. Water is the great blessing of Allah; no one can withstand without water. Everybody needs water for their survival of life. It is estimated that 70% of humans rely on water. Water is a substance specially created by Allah Almighty as the basis for life and with all its physical and chemical properties created in such a way as to support life. Millions of different life forms on earth survive utilizing water, and all the balance necessary for life are maintained using its presence.

Causes

Water Pollution is caused by many factors such as human activity and biological activities. Natural factors include storms, mud, Wind, and soil particles. Volcanos, animals waste, marine dumping, Etc. They are also included in natural resources. Artificial resources include sewage water, fertilizers, Pesticides, Etc. Water pollution is an alarming issue in the world. Domestic waste, Household waste, Industrial waste, Thermal pollution, Oxygen depletion, Denitrification, Eutrophication, Detergent's use, Acid rain are all unnatural causes produced by humans—the primary source of water pollution or contamination.

Is sewage (faecal) which is extensively discharged into drinking water systems?

Secondary sources of water pollution are the disposal of toxic chemicals from industrial effluents, pesticides, and fertilizers from agriculture sources into the water bodies. Heavy metals are transported by runoff from industries, municipalities, and urban areas. About 70% of industrial waste is dumped in water that causes water pollution. These industries release toxic chemicals into the water body. Also, waste from agriculture can cause environmental problems. Pesticides, fertilizers, and other chemicals from agricultural waste pollute the soil and water bodies. Most of these metals end up accumulating in the soil and sediment of water bodies. Heavy metals can be present in small amounts in water sources but are highly poisonous, posing significant health risks to humans and other organisms. Surface water pollution (e.g., lakes, streams, and ocean parts in marine pollution) and groundwater pollution are two types of water pollution. Water pollution can come from both point and non-point sources.

Point source: Pollution originating from a single, identifiable source, such as a discharge pipe from a factory or sewage plant, is called point-source pollution.

Non-point source: Pollution that does not originate from a single source, or point, is called nonpoint-source pollution.

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Plastics

Chlorinated plastic can release harmful chemicals into the surrounding. Soil can then seep into groundwater sources. This can cause harmful effects on the species that drink water. Plastic material may cause considerable water pollution, and these plastics can affect the aquatic environment. This plastic can deplete the oxygen content in the water sources. The oil spill also causes water problems; it will cause serious harm to marine wildlife. An oil spill can suffocate fish, get caught in the feathers of birds and mammals, and Block light from photosynthetic plants in the water. Phosphate in detergents can lead to a freshwater algal bloom that releases toxins and deplete oxygen in waterways. When the algae decompose, they use up the oxygen was available for aquatic life.

Effects

Water pollution can affect human health; it causes various diseases like Diarrhea, cholera, and typhoid. According to the UN (United Nations), approximately 297000 children under five dies from diseases linked to water pollution every year. It will cause Rashes, Respiratory problems, Neurological problems, blue baby syndrome, Stomach, liver illnesses, Risk of cancer, Etc. Water pollution causes the rapid growth of algae. It reduces the aesthetic quality of lakes and rivers. It is also unfitted for cleaning and washing as organic are decomposed naturally in the sewage by bacteria and other microorganisms. The dissolved oxygen content of water is depleted. This endangers the quality of lakes and Streams, where a high level of oxygen is required for fish and other aquatic organisms to Survive. Water is not polluted at surface level, but the groundwater also pollutes it—this Contaminated groundwater damage soil productivity. In Pakistan soil, there is a deficiency of iron, zinc, Etc. However, by giving this polluted water, we also reduce the value of these essential nutrients by a deficient level. Very harmful levels deteriorate the soil conditions. This polluted water reduces soil fertility and soil nutrient ability. We are growing our crops and vegetables on this

contaminated soil. By consuming these polluted water vegetables, human beings can have a significant health problem. These vegetables and fruits from polluted water take heavy metal and low nutrients value that healthy Persons need. These vegetables reduce the essential nutrients value like carbohydrates Etc.

Water pollution disrupts the food chain by removing the toxin from one level to higher levels in the chain; in some cases, it will destroy the entire part of the chain. This will cause (polluted water) various problems in humans, which are affected by the disease. Asia, especially India, is the most affected country by water pollution. Their water body is more petite; they have huge problems with water pollution. Around 80% of stomach ailments happen in India due to drinking contaminated water. In the world 3.4million, people die every year from water pollution. Approximately a 785million people in the world do not have access to drinking clean water.

Conclusion

This problem (water pollution) cannot be ended, but we have to control this problem independently. We should not through rubbish, plastic, and other waste materials into the water bodies, which contaminate the water bodies. Then this polluted water can cause a considerable health problem in human Beings and badly affect the aquatic environment. We should have to adopt a recycling process to use this water many times. There could be a different way of water usage like that our sink and wastewater (toilet) will be separate so that we could manage it properly, this may be costly, but for safe use of water, it is good. In our wealthy society, we should have water treatment plants that clean the water, and then this water will be used for vegetables and crops and other purposes.

"DESTROY WATER, DESTROY THE LIFE"

We should pick up the litter and garbage by hand from the water channel. Dispose of household waste properly, reduce plastic usage, Avoid Using Pesticides. Make sure to clean up dog waste by making sustainable choices for food and drinking, using phosphate-free detergent, checking your sump pump. Medical waste is disposed of safely. Report water

polluters, Aware the public, make conferences at universities and colleges, try to avoid plastic containers, never put chemicals down the drain place them outside from water system. That is, it.

"CLEAN WATER IS A BLESSING FROM GOD;
DON'T POLLUTE IT."